

MODELING OF GROUPS OF DUAL-CYCLE NON-COMMUTATIVE TWO-OPERAND CET-OPERATIONS

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Abstract *Primary research task: To develop a method for synthesis of groups of dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations; to determine the possibility of creating dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations that allow mutual transformation of direct and inverse operations by permutation of operands; to analyze and evaluate options for creating cryptographic systems based on dual-cycle CET-operations. The foundation of our research is the hypothesis regarding the possibility of synthesizing groups of the modified dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of the results, as well as the possibility to create a dual-cycle two-operand CET-operations, in which the correlation between direct and inverse operations exists through the permutation of operands. The object of research: We define the synthesis processes of groups of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations used to simplify creation of stream ciphers as the object of our study. We have defined the attributes of dual-cycle CET-operations to complete our task. Afterward, we developed and demonstrated a method applicable for synthesis of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations, which takes into account their attributes. The method provides an option to generate pseudorandom sequences of modifications of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of the results. We have also analyzed the options for creating cryptographic systems based on dual-cycle commutative and non-commutative CET-operations. In addition, we have evaluated their variability. The modeling results prove that generation of a pseudorandom sequence of mutually inverse CET-operations is impossible. We have also researched the possibility of increasing the variability of cryptographic algorithms based on the dual-cycle mutually inverse CET-operations by using additional symmetrical CET-operations. We confirm that all of the analyzed cryptographic systems have their advantages and disadvantages. Thus, we suggest defining the most suitable among the presented cryptographic algorithms based on the available resources in the data security system. We have defined the following branches as the most suitable for application of the acquired results: mobile and stationary systems of limited resources cryptographic security of the confidential data.*

Keywords: Low resource cryptography, stream encryption, CET-encryption, non-commutative CET-operations, dual-cycle CET-operations, cryptographic systems.

1. Introduction

An increased demand for data protection is the defining attribute of the last several decades. The reason for this demand lies in transition of the majority of human activities to cyberspace. In there, bank operations are carried out [1], different websites function [2-4], learning services are delivered [5, 6], and various kinds of advice and consulting including medical, legal, and political [7, 8] are given, etc. Many countries employ online monitoring and online delivery of state services [9]. In addition, the popularity of private messaging in social networks and the total amount of personal data belonging to users, who strive for confidentiality, increases annually. Correspondingly, this affects the development of cybersecurity, including methods for apprehending cyber terrorists and reducing the rate of cybercrimes. Thus, an increase in demand for data security complexifies the demands for data security systems, including those utilized in cryptography. These demands include the capability to quickly process large volumes of data (preferably in real-time), high cryptographic integrity, support for hardware and software implementation, the capability to operate with limited resources, etc. [10, 11]. Finally, cryptographic systems implemented for data protection require substantial improvements related to their security against post-quantum cryptographic analysis [12-14].

Low resource and post-quantum cryptography are one way of improving the systems used for data protection. The value of the low resource cryptography revolves around the possibility of its broad implementation on different devices, such as mobile phones, tablets, different kinds of smart systems, as well as other gadgets [15, 17]. CET encryption, which relies on the creation of stream ciphers based on CET operations, is among the most promising ways for development of the low resource cryptography [18]. Implementing CET operations, which allow permutation of operands, in stream ciphers provides an option to double the amount of substitution tables implemented during the creation of cryptograms.

2. Analysis of sources and target setting

Research of CET-operations that allow permutation of operands primarily focuses on symmetrical CET-operations [19, 20]. The symmetrical CET-operations that allow permutation of operands are commutative since a cryptogram remains unaffected by the permutation. Application of commutative CET-operations does not increase the number of used substitution tables. A commutative CET-operation is applicable for both encryption and decryption, allowing addressees of a cryptographic system to use cryptograms based on the identical substitution tables unaffected by the permutation of operands [18]. However, the attribute mentioned above does not apply when a non-commutative CET-operation, which allows permutation of operands, is used. We have classified these non-commutative CET-operations, which allows permutation of operands based on transposition ciphers [21], into operations of dual and triple cycles. Models of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations created based on simulation experiment are described in [22]. It is, however, worth noting that application of simulation

experiments for creating CET-operations is a complex process. Thus, we suggest developing an analytical method for synthesis of groups of non-commutative CET-operations, which is identical to the method used for synthesis of groups of commutative (symmetrical) CET-operations that allow permutation of operands [19, 20]. We also suggest developing a simplified method for synthesizing non-commutative CET-operations to create stream ciphers simply.

3. Purpose and objectives of research

The purpose of this research lies in developing a method applicable for the synthesis of groups of dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations, the usage of which provides an option to create stream encryption algorithms based on permutations of operands.

We have established the following objectives to fulfill the aforementioned purpose:

- to study the attributes of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations;
- to synthesize a group of modified dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of transformation results;
- to develop a model of synthesis of groups of dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations;
- to define the rules for creating the dual-cycle CET-operations capable of ensuring the mutual transformation of direct and inverse operations by permutation of operands;
- to apply the developed model of synthesis of groups of CET-operations to modify the dual-cycle CET-operations capable of ensuring the mutual transformation of direct and inverse operations by permutation of operands;
- to evaluate the application of the developed groups of CET-operations in stream ciphers created by using them as their foundation.

4. Materials and methods

We define the synthesis processes of groups of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations used to simplify creation of stream ciphers as the object of our research.

The primary hypothesis of our research is the possibility of synthesizing the groups of modified dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of transformation results. We also attempt to prove the hypothesis regarding the possibility of creating dual-cycle two-operand CET-operations, in which the direct and inverse operations are connected through permutation of operands.

Proving our primary hypothesis, however, revolves around improving the method of synthesis of groups of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations. By doing so, we can ensure the successful synthesis of groups of modified dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations. The correctness of the acquired results allows ensuring the correlation between the synthesized models of

operations and the results of simulation experiment. We have utilized methods of discrete mathematics, linear algebra, and theory of sets to define the creation rules and limitations of dual-cycle CET-operations capable of ensuring the mutual transformation of direct and inverse operations by permutation of operands.

To provide the most accurate description of the specified tasks, as well as to depict the acquired results most accurately, we have used only those CET-operations, the models of which were created based on modulo 2 addition. We explain this limitation of ours by the fact that only one mathematical apparatus can be used to describe a CET-operation, as well as the presentation simplicity and the possibility of mutual transformation of their models.

5. Modeling results of groups of dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations

5.1. Dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations

We will now analyze the attributes of dual-cycle CET-operations.

Any kind of CET-operation can be defined as a discrete model of one or several substitution tables [18]. A single-operand CET-operation operates with a single substitution table. A single-operand CET-operation $C(x)$ has an inverse CET-operation $C'(x)$, whereas $C'(C(x)) = x$. A two-operand CET-operation is a tuple of single-operand operations $C(x, y) = C(C_1(x), C_2(x), C_3(x), \dots, C_n(x))$. It operates with several substitution tables. A two-operand CET-operation $C(x, y)$ has an inverse CET-operation $C'(x, y) = C(C'_1(x), C'_2(x), C'_3(x), \dots, C'_n(x))$, whereas $C'(C(x, y), y) = x$.

Certain two-operand CET-operations allow permutation of operands. According to the results of simulation experiment [24], there is a total of 24 groups of two-digit two-operand CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of the results that allow permutation of operands. A two-operand CET-operation $C(x, y)$ allows permutation of operands if there is a CET-operation $C(y, x)$.

A two-operand CET-operation $C(x, y)$ is considered commutative if $C(x, y) = C(y, x)$ [25]. A two-operand commutative CET-operation $C(x, y)$ is considered symmetrical if $C(x, y) = C(y, x) = C'(x, y) = C'(y, x)$. According to the results of the conducted simulation experiment, we have defined a total of 4 groups of symmetrical commutative CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of transformation results.

A two-operand CET-operation $C(x, y)$ is considered non-commutative if $C(x, y) \neq C(y, x)$ [18]. According to the results of the conducted simulation experiment, we have defined a total of 20 groups of symmetrical non-commutative CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of transformation results. We operate with definitions “dual-cycle” and “triple-cycle” specifically to describe these groups [21].

A two-operand non-commutative CET-operation $C(x, y)$ is considered a dual-cycle CET-operation if $C(x, y) \in C^*(x, y)$; $C(y, x) \in C^*(x, y)$, where $C^*(x, y)$ is a group of operations to an accuracy of permutation of the results. Direct and inverse operations in two-operand non-commutative CET-operations are a part of the same group of operations to an accuracy of permutation of the results.

One of our suggestions is defining a group of mutually inverse operations among the dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations. A dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operation $C(x, y)$ is considered mutually inverse if $C(y, x) = C'(x, y)$. Because $C(x, y) \in C^*(x, y)$ and $C(y, x) \in C^*(x, y)$, then the following expression $C(x, y) = C'(y, x)$ is valid. Permutation of operands in mutually inverse dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations allows mutual transformation of direct and inverse operations. The data encrypted by a direct operation (without permutation of operands) is decrypted by an inverse operation (with permuted operands). Correspondingly, the data encrypted by an inverse operation (with permuted operands) is decrypted by a direct operation (without permutation of operands).

A two-operand non-commutative CET-operation $C(x, y)$ is considered a triple-cycle CET-operation if $C(x, y) \in C^*(x, y)$; $C(y, x) \notin C^*(x, y)$, where $C^*(x, y)$ is a group of operations to an accuracy of permutation of the results. Permutation of operands in a triple-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations requires identification of an inverse operation among other groups of operation to an accuracy of permutation of the results.

A set of mutually inverse dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations is a subset of dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations. The results of our simulation experiment allow us to establish that sets of dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations form groups of CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of the results [22]. We will now analyze the synthesis of groups of dual-cycle two-digit non-commutative two-operand CET-operations.

5.2. Synthesis of groups of dual-cycle two-digit non-commutative two-operand CET-operations

We have utilized synthesis methods described in [19, 20] to synthesize symmetrical commutative CET-operations. These synthesis methods modify the specified symmetrical commutative operation by a group of single-operand CET-operations. This approach can have a broader application considering that symmetrical commutative CET-operations can be considered a subtype of dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations.

We will now analyze the possibility of applying the approach mentioned above for creating a group of dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations. Overall, the application of this method for synthesis of a dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operation is possible when the following conditions are met:

- The specified operation must be a dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operation;
- The elementary functions of the specified operation must be considered as variables of a single-operand CET-operation.

We can consider this method for synthesizing groups of dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations identical to the method for synthesizing groups of operation to an accuracy of permutation of the result by taking into account the conditions mentioned above.

Modification of the specified two-operand CET-operation to an accuracy of permutation is described by model:

$$C(x, y) = C_i(C(x, y)), \tag{1}$$

where $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$; m is a number of single-operand CET-operations in a group.

The method utilized for synthesis of a group of two-operand CET-operations an accuracy of permutation requires sequential implementation of the specified transformation model (1) for all single-operand CET-operations.

We will now analyze the implementation of the same method by using the creation process of two-bit dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations as an example. A group of two-bit single-operand CET-operations is required for proper illustration of this example. The group of two-bit single-operand CET-operations is described in Table 1 [23].

Table 1

The group of two bit single-operand CET-operations [9]

$C_1(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_7(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{13}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{19}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_2(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_8(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{14}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{20}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_3(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_9(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{15}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{21}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_4(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{10}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{16}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{22}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_5(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{11}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{17}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{23}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_6(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{12}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{18}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{24}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$

We will utilize a group of models of dual-cycle two-operand CET-operations described in [22] and acquired as a result of the simulation experiment to prove the correctness of the utilized method, as well as the results of modification of non-commutative CET-operations. We consider the synthesis

method correct if it is possible to create all CET-operations from the specified group by utilizing the specified operation from this group.

We define the following CET-operation as specified:

$$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

We will now conduct the first modification of operation (2) based on a single-operand CET-operation

$$C_1(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

We acquire the following result by replacing x_1 and x_2 in operation (3) with elementary functions $f_1(x, y) = x_1 \oplus y_1$ and $f_2(x, y) = x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2$ from operation (2):

$$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} f_1(x, y) \\ f_2(x, y) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

The elementary functions in operation (2) depend on two variables x and y . For this reason, the model of the modified CET-operation will depend on the two variables as well, while the operation itself will be a two-operand CET-operation. The single-operand CET-operation (3) is considered a null operation in a group of single-operand CET-operations. As such, the incoming data is unaffected by its implementation. The fact that models (2) and (4) are identical proves that modification of the specified CET-operation (2) by a single-operand CET-operation (3) does not alter the model of an operation.

We acquire the following model of CET-operation by permutating the operands in a model of CET-operation (4):

$$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

We will now modify a CET-operation (2) based on a single-operand CET-operation $C_2(x)$.

We acquire the following model by replacing the variables x_1 and x_2 by the elementary functions $f_1(x, y) = x_1 \oplus y_1$ and $f_2(x, y) = x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2$ from operation (2) in a model of a single-operand CET-operation $C_2(x)$:

$$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} f_1(x, y) \oplus f_2(x, y) \\ f_2(x, y) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

We acquire the following model of CET-operation by permutating the operands in a model of CET-operation (6):

$$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

We will now modify a CET-operation (2) based on a single-operand CET-operation $C_3(x)$.

We acquire the following model by replacing the variables x_1 and x_2 by the elementary functions $f_1(x, y) = x_1 \oplus y_1$ and $f_2(x, y) = x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2$ from operation (2) in a model of a single-operand CET-operation $C_3(x)$:

$$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} f_1(x, y) \\ f_1(x, y) \oplus f_2(x, y) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{8}$$

We acquire the following model of CET-operation by permutating the operands in a model of CET-operation (6):

$$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} \tag{9}$$

Following the procedure described earlier, we have created all 24 modifications of the model of CET-operation (2) to an accuracy of permutation of the results. We have also created a model of CET-operation after permutation of operands has taken place for each modification. The modeling results for a group of models of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations are illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2

Synthesized group of models of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations

$C(x)$	Inversion operations			
	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_1(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_2(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_3(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_4(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_5(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_6(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$

The synthesized group of models of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations (table 1) is identical to the group of models of dual-cycle two-operand CET-operations, which was created based on the results of simulation experiment [22]. This allows us to conclude that the proposed method for synthesis of groups of models of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations is correct.

The synthesis method described above is applicable for generating the sequences of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations. This results in a significant increase in decryption difficulty, thus making it much harder for an intruder to get access to the cryptogram.

5.3. Synthesis of mutually inverse two bit dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations

We will now analyze the possibility of utilizing a dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operation as a mutually inverse two-operand CET-operation. The possibility of modifying a direct operation into an inverse operation by permutating the operands can be checked by comparing an inverse operation with the modified one.

As an example, we will use the previous CET-operation (2), which was specified for synthesis of a group of non-commutative two-operand CET-operation. Permutation of operands will modify this CET-operation (2) into CET-operation (5). We will now create an inverse CET-operation for operation (2). To do so, we will describe the operation (2) by a tuple of single-operand CET-operations:

$$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{cases} C_1(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ C_3(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ C_{19}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ C_{13}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases}$$

Two-operand CET-operation $C'(x, y)$ will be inverse for two-operand CET-operation $C(x, y)$ if the former is created based on the tuple of single-operand CET-operations.

Table 3 presents a classified group of two bit single-operand CET-operations, which are divided into symmetrical and non-symmetrical. Non-symmetrical operations are represented by pairs of operations for direct and inverse transformation and are highlighted in gray.

According to Table 3, the following result is acquired by substituting inverse single-operand CET-operations into an inverse two-operand CET-operation:

$$C'(x, y) = \begin{cases} C'_1(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ C'_3(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ C'_{19}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ C'_{13}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Comparing models (5) and (10) allows us to conclude that $C(y, x) \neq C'(x, y)$, meaning that operation (2) is not a mutually inverse CET-operation.

Table 3

The group of two bit single-operand CET-operations

$C_1(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_7(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{13}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{19}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_2(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_8(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{14}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{20}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C'_8(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$		$C'_{20}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_3(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_9(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{15}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{21}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
		$C'_{15}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{21}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_4(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{10}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{16}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{22}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C'_{10}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{16}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	
$C_5(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{11}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{17}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{23}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C'_5(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{11}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{17}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{23}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_6(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{12}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{18}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{24}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C'_6(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{12}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{18}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{24}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$

Synthesizing groups of CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of operands based on model (1) provides the following possibilities:

- Synthesis of groups of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations, if a dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operation is designated as the specified operation;
- Synthesis of groups of symmetrical commutative CET-operations, if a symmetrical commutative operation is designated as the specified operation [20]. The described CET-operations are the dual-cycle CET-operations;

Mutually inverse CET-operations are considered dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations. Let's assume, that there is a possibility to synthesize a group of mutually inverse CET-operations based on model (1), if a mutually inverse non-commutative operation is designated as the specified operation.

To prove this hypothesis, we must first create the specified mutually inverse CET-operation.

Mutually inverse dual-cycle CET-operations exist under the following conditions:

$$\begin{cases} C(x, y) \neq C(y, x); \\ C(x, y) \neq C'(x, y); \\ C(y, x) = C'(x, y); \\ C(x, y) = C'(y, x). \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

According to (11), a mutually inverse dual-cycle CET-operation can be described in the following way:

$$C(x, y) = C(x) \oplus C'(y), \quad (12)$$

where $C(x) \neq C'(x)$.

The following expression $C(y, x) = C(y) \oplus C'(x)$, where $C(y) \neq C'(y)$, is valid, since CET-operation (12) is a dual-cycle operation.

We will now create mutually inverse two-bit dual-cycle CET-operations, which may be specified to create a group of operations based on model (1). We will utilize two-bit CET-operations from Table 3 to complete this task. We will also enumerate the synthesized two-operand CET-operations based on the numbers of single-operand CET-operations, from which they are synthesized, to simplify the presentation of the results.

According to Table 3, the following two-bit single-operand CET-operations

$$\begin{aligned} C_1(x) &= C'_1(x), \\ C_2(x) &= C'_2(x), \\ C_3(x) &= C'_3(x), \\ C_4(x) &= C'_4(x), \\ C_7(x) &= C'_7(x), \\ C_9(x) &= C'_9(x), \\ C_{13}(x) &= C'_{13}(x), \\ C_{14}(x) &= C'_{14}(x), \\ C_{19}(x) &= C'_{19}(x), \\ C_{22}(x) &= C'_{22}(x), \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

are symmetrical. It is, however, impossible to synthesize the mutually inverse CET-operations based on the symmetrical single-operand CET-operations mentioned above.

We will now analyze two-bit non-symmetrical single-operand CET-operations.

The following expression is valid for operation $C_5(x)$: $C_5(x) \neq C_5'(x)$. This expression is applicable for utilization in the model (12) to create the following dual-cycle mutually inverse CET-operation:

$$C_5(x, y) = C_5(x) \oplus C_5'(y) \quad (14)$$

We acquire the following results by substituting a model of direct ($C_5(x)$) and inverse ($C_5'(x)$) single-operand CET-operations from table 3 into model (14):

$$C_5(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

We acquire the following result by permutating the operands in a model of CET-operation:

$$C_5(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (16)$$

We acquire the following result by permutating the operands in the model (15):

$$C_5(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

According to $C_5(x, y) \neq C_5(y, x)$ and $C_5(y, x) \neq C_5(x, y)$, the CET-operation synthesized based on model (14) is a dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operation.

We will now determine whether the operation (15) corresponds with the conditions for mutually inverse operations or not.

First, we define an inverse CET-operation for operation (15).

$$C_5(x, y) = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{cases} C_5(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ C_{23}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ C_{17}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ C_{11}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$C'_5(x, y) = \begin{cases} C'_5(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ C'_{23}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ C'_{17}(x), & \text{if } k_1 = y; y_2 = 0 \\ C'_{11}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Afterward, we do the same for operation (16).

$$C_5(y, x) = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{cases} C_6(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ C_{12}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ C_{24}(x), & \text{if } k_1 = y; y_2 = 0 \\ C_{18}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$C'_5(y, x) = \begin{cases} C'_6(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ C'_{12}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ C'_{24}(x), & \text{if } k_1 = y; y_2 = 0 \\ C'_{18}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Because $C_5(y, x) = C'_5(x, y)$ and $C_5(x, y) = C'_5(y, x)$, the synthesized CET-operation (15) is mutually inverse.

CET-operation $C_6(x)$ corresponds with the conditions of the following expression: $C_6(x) \neq C'_6(x)$.

We acquire the following results according to model (12):

$$C_6(x, y) = C_6(x) \oplus C'_6(y);$$

$$C_6(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}; \tag{18}$$

$$C_6(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{19}$$

We can make the following conclusions based on our analysis of models (15)-(19):

Because the expressions $C_5(x, y) = C_6(y, x)$ and $C_5(y, x) = C_6(x, y)$ are valid, the expressions $C_6(x, y) = C_6'(y, x)$ and $C_6(y, x) = C_6'(x, y)$ are valid as well. Therefore, CET-operation $C_6(x, y)$ is mutually inverse.

Permutation of operands in CET-operation $C_5(x, y)$ results in implementation of CET-operation $C_6(x, y)$. Permutation of operands in CET-operation $C_6(x, y)$ results in implementation of CET-operation $C_5(x, y)$.

CET-operation $C_8(x)$ corresponds with the conditions of the following expression: $C_8(x) \neq C_8'(x)$.

We acquire the following results based on model (12):

$$C_8(x, y) = C_8(x) \oplus C_8'(y)$$

$$C_8(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix};$$

$$C_8(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Because $C_8(x, y) = C_8(y, x)$, the synthesized CET-operation is a dual-cycle commutative operation. Thus, it cannot fulfill the role of the specified operation for synthesis of a group of mutually inverse operations.

CET-operation $C_{10}(x)$ corresponds with the conditions of the following expression: $C_{10}(x) \neq C_{10}'(x)$.

We acquire the following results based on model (12):

$$C_{10}(x, y) = C_{10}(x) \oplus C_{10}'(y)$$

$$C_{10}(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix};$$

$$C_{10}(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Because $C_{10}(x, y) = C_{10}(y, x)$, CET-operation $C_{10}(x, y)$ cannot fulfill the role of the specified operation for synthesis of a group of mutually inverse operations.

Correspondingly, CET-operations $C_{15}(x, y)$, $C_{16}(x, y)$, $C_{20}(x, y)$, and $C_{21}(x, y)$ are also considered dual-cycle commutative operations and cannot fulfill the role of the specified operations for synthesis of groups of mutually inverse operations.

We will now create a CET-operation $C(x, y)$ based on CET-operation $C_{11}(x)$, which corresponds with expression $C_{11}(x) \neq C_{11}'(x)$.

We acquire the following results based on model (12):

$$C_{11}(x, y) = C_{11}(x) \oplus C_{11}'(y);$$

$$C_{11}(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix};$$

$$C_{11}(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix};$$

$$C_{11}(x, y) \neq C_{11}(y, x).$$

Because $C_{11}(x, y) = C_5(x, y)$ and $C_{11}(y, x) = C_5(y, x)$, CET-operation $C_{11}(x, y)$ is a mutually inverse dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operation.

We acquire identical result with CET-operations $C_{17}(x, y)$ and $C_{23}(x, y)$, which are created based on single-operand CET-operations $C_{17}(x)$ and $C_{23}(x)$.

We will now create a CET-operation $C(x, y)$ based on CET-operation $C_{12}(x)$, which corresponds with expression $C_{12}(x) \neq C'_{12}(x)$.

We acquire the following results based on model (12):

$$C_{12}(x, y) = C_{12}(x) \oplus C'_{12}(y);$$

$$C_{12}(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix};$$

$$C_{12}(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix};$$

$$C_{12}(x, y) \neq C_{12}(y, x).$$

Because $C_{12}(x, y) = C_6(x, y)$ and $C_{12}(y, x) = C_6(y, x)$, CET-operation $C_{12}(x, y)$ is a mutually inverse dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operation.

We acquire identical result with CET-operations $C_{18}(x, y)$ and $C_{24}(x, y)$, which are created based on single-operand CET-operations $C_{18}(x)$ and $C_{24}(x)$.

The acquired results prove that only two mutually inverse two-bit dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations can be created based on model (12). These are operations $C_5(x, y)$ and $C_6(x, y)$. These operations can be specified for synthesis of groups of mutually inverse two-bit dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations.

We will now synthesize a group of two-bit dual-cycle two-operand CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of the results based on model (1). We define $C_5(x, y)$ as the specified CET-operation.

We conduct the synthesis based on $C_5(x, y)$ according to the following model:

$$C_5(x, y) = C_i(C_5(x, y)) \text{ where } i \in \{1, \dots, 24\}$$

Model of the specified CET-operation $C_5(x, y)$ implements elementary functions $f_1(x, y) = x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2$ and $f_2(x, y) = x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2$.

Modification of the specified CET-operation $C_5(x, y)$ by a single-operand CET-operation $C_1(x)$ does not alter the specified operation. Thus, a modified CET-operation is considered mutually inverse as well.

We will now modify a CET-operation $C_5(x, y)$ by a single-operand CET-operation $C_2(x)$. We acquire the following result by replacing the variables x_1 and x_2 by the elementary functions $f_1(x, y)$ and $f_2(x, y)$ in CET-operation $C_2(x)$:

$$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} f_1(x, y) \oplus f_2(x, y) \\ f_2(x, y) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2) \oplus (x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2) \\ (x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Permutating the operands implements the following model:

$$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

$$C(x, y) \neq C(y, x)$$

We will now proceed to find an inverse CET-operation for $C(x, y)$.

$$C(x, y) = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{cases} C_3(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ C_9(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ C_{15}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ C_{21}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$C'(x, y) = \begin{cases} C'_3(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ C'_9(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ C'_{15}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ C'_{21}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Because $C(y, x) \neq C'(x, y)$, modification of the specified CET-operation $C_5(x, y)$ by a single-operand CET-operation $C_2(x)$ does not result in acquisition of a new mutually inverse CET-operation.

We will now modify a CET-operation $C_5(x, y)$ by a single-operand CET-operation $C_3(x)$.

$$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} f_1(x, y) \\ f_1(x, y) \oplus f_2(x, y) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2) \\ (x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2) \oplus (x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Permutating the operands implements the following model:

$$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

$$C(x, y) \neq C(y, x)$$

We will now proceed to find an inverse CET-operation for $C(x, y)$.

$$C(x, y) = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{cases} C_4(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ C_{16}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ C_{22}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ C_{10}(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$C'(x, y) = \begin{cases} C'_4(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0 \\ C'_{16}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1 \\ C'_{22}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0 \\ C'_{10}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Unfortunately, modification of the specified CET-operation by a single-operand CET-operation $C_3(x)$ does not create a new mutually inverse CET-operation.

Overall, we have created all 24 modifications of a model of CET-operation $C_5(x, y)$ to an accuracy of permutation of the results, models of CET-operations after permutation of operands, as well as inverse CET-operations.

The results of creating a group of models of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations, which were synthesized based on $C_5(x, y)$ to an accuracy of permutation of the results, are described in Table 4.

Table 4 contains model of direct CET-operation ($C(x, y)$), CET-operation with permuted operands ($C(y, x)$), and a model of inverse CET-operation ($C'(x, y)$) for every modification of CET-operation $C_5(x, y)$. As we can determine from Table 4, the expression $C(y, x) = C'(x, y)$ is valid for only two modifications $C_5(x, y)$. These operations are mutually inverse. Mutually inverse operations in Table 4 are highlighted in gray.

Table 4

Group of models of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations, which were synthesized based on $C_5(x, y)$

$C(x)$	Inversion operations			
	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$
$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}$

Modeling results of a group of two-bit dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of the results show that this group contains only two mutually inverse dual-cycle CET-operations. We can designate any CET-operation from this group as specified to synthesize a group of dual-cycle

non-commutative CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation. Thus, a change of the specified operation will not alter a CET-operation in the synthesized group. This change of the specified CET-operation can, however, alter the pseudorandom sequence of the synthesized two-operand CET-operations if the pseudorandom sequences of single-operand CET-operations are identical.

We can see that the number of dual-cycle mutually inverse non-commutative CET-operations acquired based on model (1) is identical to the number of mutually inverse CET-operations acquired based on model (12).

We will now analyze the modeling results of mutually inverse CET-operations acquired based on model (12). First of all, we illustrate the defined conditions for existence of mutually inverse CET-operations $C_i(x, y)$, where $i \in \{1, \dots, 24\}$, in the form of a table. The table divides the subgroups of two-bit single-operand CET-operations in basic operations, permutation operations, and inversion operations. We will now place the existence conditions of i mutually inverse CET-operation according to the single-operand CET-operation, based on which it was created. Single-operand CET-operations are placed at the intersection of rows of basic operations and permutation operations with columns of inversion operations. A single-operand operation is presented as a modulo 2 addition of a basic or permutation operation to an inversion operation.

The defined existence conditions for mutually inverse two-bit CET-operations are presented in table 5.

Table 5

Analysis of the results of creating mutually inverse CET-operations based to model (12)

$C(x)$		Inversion operations			
		$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$
Basic operations	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_1(x, y) = C_1(y, x)$	$C_7(x, y) = C_7(y, x)$	$C_{13}(x, y) = C_{13}(y, x)$	$C_{19}(x, y) = C_{19}(y, x)$
	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_2(x, y) = C_2(y, x)$	$C_8(x, y) = C_8(y, x)$	$C_{14}(x, y) = C_{14}(y, x)$	$C_{20}(x, y) = C_{20}(y, x)$
	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_3(x, y) = C_3(y, x)$	$C_9(x, y) = C_9(y, x)$	$C_{15}(x, y) = C_{15}(y, x)$	$C_{21}(x, y) = C_{21}(y, x)$
Permutation operations	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_4(x, y) = C_4(y, x)$	$C_{10}(x, y) = C_{10}(y, x)$	$C_{16}(x, y) = C_{16}(y, x)$	$C_{22}(x, y) = C_{22}(y, x)$
	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_5(x, y) \neq C_5(y, x)$	$C_{11}(x, y) \neq C_{11}(y, x)$	$C_{17}(x, y) \neq C_{17}(y, x)$	$C_{23}(x, y) \neq C_{23}(y, x)$
	$C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_5(y, x) = C'_5(x, y)$	$C_{11}(y, x) \neq C'_{11}(x, y)$	$C_{17}(y, x) \neq C'_{17}(x, y)$	$C_{23}(y, x) \neq C'_{23}(x, y)$
	$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_6(x, y) \neq C_6(y, x)$	$C_{12}(x, y) \neq C_{11}(y, x)$	$C_{18}(x, y) \neq C_{18}(y, x)$	$C_{24}(x, y) \neq C_{24}(y, x)$
	$C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_6(y, x) = C'_6(x, y)$	$C_{12}(y, x) \neq C'_{11}(x, y)$	$C_{18}(y, x) \neq C'_{18}(x, y)$	$C_{24}(y, x) \neq C'_{24}(x, y)$

The analysis of Table 5 proves the following:

- Mutually inverse two-operand CET-operation is impossible to create based on symmetrical single-operand CET-operations. Conditions suitable for creating such operations are highlighted in bright yellow in Table 5.
- If a single-operand CET-operation from either the base group or the group of permutation operations is symmetrical, then combining this operation with inverse operations results in the acquisition of commutative CET-operation. This operation is considered commutative only when permutation of operands takes place. Conditions suitable for creating such operations are highlighted in dark yellow in table 5. Overall, combining symmetrical single-operand CET-operations from either the base group or the group of permutation operations with inversion operations by utilizing modulo 2 addition does not allow creating mutually inverse non-commutative CET-operations;
- A mutually inverse dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operation is created based on model (12) from non-symmetrical single-operand CET-operations from either the base group or the group of permutation operations. Conditions suitable for creating such operations are highlighted in dark green in Table 5;
- If a single-operand CET-operation from either the base group or the group of permutation operations is non-symmetrical, then combining this operation with inverse operations results in acquisition of non-commutative CET-operation. The acquired non-commutative CET-operation will not, however, be mutually inverse. Conditions suitable for creating such operations are highlighted in bright green in Table 5. As we can determine from Table 5, modification of a mutually inverse dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operation results in the acquisition of non-commutative CET-operation that is not mutually inverse.

The results of our analysis allow us to conclude that synthesizing a full set of mutually inverse dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations is possible by combining direct and inverse non-symmetrical single-operand CET-operations from the base group and group of permutation operations.

We will now create three-bit mutually inverse non-commutative two-operand CET-operations based on the results mentioned above. We can achieve this by combining single-operand operations, the elementary functions of which are created based on modulo 2 addition. We define these single-operand CET-operations as matrix operations due to the conducted linear transformations [20]. Correspondingly, we define the two-operand CET-operations synthesized based on single-operand matrix operations as matrix operations as well.

5.4. Synthesis of mutually inverse three-bit dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand matrix CET-operations

We utilize the base group of three-bit single-operand matrix operations [20] consisting of 28 CET-operations for synthesis of mutually inverse three-bit dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand matrix CET-operations. This base group is described in table 6.

Table 6

Base group of three bit single-operand matrix CET-operations [20]

$C_1(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_2(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_3(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_4(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_5(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_6(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_7(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_8(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_9(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{10}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{11}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{12}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_{13}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{14}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{15}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{16}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$
	$C'_{14}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{15}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{16}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_{17}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{18}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{19}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{20}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$
$C'_{17}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{18}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{19}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{20}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_{21}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{22}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{23}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{24}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$
$C'_{21}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{22}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{23}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{24}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$
$C_{25}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{26}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{27}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C_{28}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$
$C'_{25}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{26}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{27}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$	$C'_{28}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}$

We will now analyze the creation of mutually inverse three-bit non-commutative two-operand matrix CET-operations. According to Table 6, $C_{14}(x)$ is the first non-symmetrical CET-operation from the base group.

We create the following two-operand CET-operation based on model $C_{14}(x, y) = C_{14}(x) \oplus C'_{14}(y)$ where $C_{14}(x) \neq C'_{14}(x)$:

$$C_{14}(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

We will now define whether this model (20) is mutually inverse.

At first, we acquire the model of operation by permutating operands in $C_{14}(x, y)$.

$$C_{14}(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Then we create an inverse operation $C'_{14}(x, y)$. Next, we present the model of a two-operand operation as a tuple of single-operand operations:

$$C_{14}(x, y) = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \end{cases},$$

Because

$$\begin{aligned}
 C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}; & C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}; \\
 C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}; & C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}; \\
 C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}; & C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}; \\
 C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}; & C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix};
 \end{aligned}$$

we acquire the following results:

$$C'_{14}(x, y) = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_2 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Because $C_{14}(y, x) \neq C'_{14}(x, y)$, the model of CET-operation (20) is not mutually inverse. $C_{15}(x)$ (Table 6) is the next non-symmetrical CET-operation from the base group.

We create the following two-operand CET-operation based on the model $C_{15}(x, y) = C_{15}(x) \oplus C'_{145}(y)$ where $C_{14}(x) \neq C'_{14}(x)$:

$$C_{15}(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{21}$$

We will now define whether this model (21) is mutually inverse.

At first, we acquire the model of operation by permutating operands in $C_{15}(x, y)$.

$$C_{15}(y, x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Then we create an inverse operation to operation $C_{15}(x, y)$:

$$C_{15}(x, y) = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \end{cases}$$

Because

$$\begin{aligned}
 C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}; & C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}; \\
 C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}; & C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}; \\
 C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}; & C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}; \\
 C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}; & C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix};
 \end{aligned}$$

we acquire the following results:

$$C'_{15}(x, y) = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Because $C_{15}(y, x) = C'_{15}(x, y)$, model (21) transforms from direct into an inverse when operands are permuted.

We will now create an inverse operation to operation $C_{15}(y, x)$:

$$C_{15}(y, x) = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{якщо } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{якщо } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{якщо } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{якщо } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{якщо } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{якщо } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{якщо } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{якщо } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \end{cases}$$

Because

$$\begin{aligned} C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}; & C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}; \\ C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}; & C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}; \\ C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}; & C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix} &\Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}; \end{aligned}$$

$$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}; \quad C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_2 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow C'(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix},$$

we acquire the following results:

$$C'_{15}(x, y) = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus 1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \end{cases} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \oplus y_1 \\ x_1 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_2 \oplus y_3 \\ x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_3 \oplus y_1 \oplus y_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

The acquired modeling results show that $C_{15}(x, y) = C'_{15}(y, x)$ and $C_{15}(y, x) = C'_{15}(x, y)$. Thus, model (21) corresponds with conditions for mutually inverse dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations.

We have also analyzed the results of creating non-commutative two-operand CET-operations based on combining non-symmetrical single-operand operations from the base group highlighted in Table 6. We have then presented the results of our analysis of created models of non-commutative two-operand CET-operations based on combining direct and inverse three-bit matrix single-operand CET-operations from the base group in the form of a table.

This Table 7 describes the results of our research related to combining direct and inverse single-operand operations into two-operand operations.

These results prove the following:

- Single-operand CET-operations $C_1(x) - C_{13}(x)$ can be utilized to create commutative dual-cycle two-operand CET-operations. The results acquired from analysis of these two-operand CET-operations are highlighted in yellow;
- Single-operand CET-operations $C_{14}(x) - C_{28}(x)$ can be utilized to create non-commutative dual-cycle two-operand CET-operations. The results acquired from analysis of these two-operand CET-operations are highlighted in blue;
- Only one single-operand CET-operation ($C_{15}(x)$) can be utilized to create non-commutative mutually inverse dual-cycle two-operand CET-operation. The results acquired from analysis of this two-operand CET-operation are highlighted in green.

Table 7

The results of analysis of created three-bit non-commutative two-operand CET-operations based on model (12)

$C_1(x, y) = C_1(y, x)$ $C_1(y, x) = C'_1(x, y)$	$C_2(x, y) = C_2(y, x)$ $C_2(y, x) = C'_2(x, y)$	$C_3(x, y) = C_3(y, x)$ $C_3(y, x) = C'_3(x, y)$	$C_4(x, y) = C_4(y, x)$ $C_4(y, x) = C'_4(x, y)$
$C_5(x, y) = C_5(y, x)$ $C_5(y, x) = C'_5(x, y)$	$C_6(x, y) = C_6(y, x)$ $C_6(y, x) = C'_6(x, y)$	$C_7(x, y) = C_7(y, x)$ $C_7(y, x) = C'_7(x, y)$	$C_8(x, y) = C_8(y, x)$ $C_8(y, x) = C'_8(x, y)$
$C_9(x, y) = C_9(y, x)$ $C_9(y, x) = C'_9(x, y)$	$C_{10}(x, y) = C_{10}(y, x)$ $C_{10}(y, x) = C'_{10}(x, y)$	$C_{11}(x, y) = C_{11}(y, x)$ $C_{11}(y, x) = C'_{11}(x, y)$	$C_{12}(x, y) = C_{12}(y, x)$ $C_{12}(y, x) = C'_{12}(x, y)$
$C_{13}(x, y) = C_{13}(y, x)$ $C_{13}(y, x) = C'_{13}(x, y)$	$C_{14}(x, y) \neq C_{14}(y, x)$ $C_{14}(y, x) \neq C'_{14}(x, y)$	$C_{15}(x, y) \neq C_{15}(y, x)$ $C_{15}(y, x) = C'_{15}(x, y)$	$C_{16}(x, y) \neq C_{16}(y, x)$ $C_{16}(y, x) \neq C'_{16}(x, y)$
$C_{17}(x, y) \neq C_{17}(y, x)$ $C_{17}(y, x) \neq C'_{17}(x, y)$	$C_{18}(x, y) \neq C_{18}(y, x)$ $C_{18}(y, x) \neq C'_{18}(x, y)$	$C_{19}(x, y) \neq C_{19}(y, x)$ $C_{19}(y, x) \neq C'_{19}(x, y)$	$C_{20}(x, y) \neq C_{20}(y, x)$ $C_{20}(y, x) \neq C'_{20}(x, y)$
$C_{21}(x, y) \neq C_{21}(y, x)$ $C_{21}(y, x) \neq C'_{21}(x, y)$	$C_{22}(x, y) \neq C_{22}(y, x)$ $C_{22}(y, x) \neq C'_{22}(x, y)$	$C_{23}(x, y) \neq C_{23}(y, x)$ $C_{23}(y, x) \neq C'_{23}(x, y)$	$C_{24}(x, y) \neq C_{24}(y, x)$ $C_{24}(y, x) \neq C'_{24}(x, y)$
$C_{25}(x, y) \neq C_{25}(y, x)$ $C_{25}(y, x) \neq C'_{25}(x, y)$	$C_{26}(x, y) \neq C_{26}(y, x)$ $C_{26}(y, x) \neq C'_{26}(x, y)$	$C_{27}(x, y) \neq C_{27}(y, x)$ $C_{27}(y, x) \neq C'_{27}(x, y)$	$C_{28}(x, y) \neq C_{28}(y, x)$ $C_{28}(y, x) \neq C'_{28}(x, y)$

The results highlighted in Table 7 prove that combining direct and inverse non-symmetrical single-operand operations does not guarantee the possibility of synthesizing the non-commutative dual-cycle mutually inverse two-operand CET-operations.

We will now analyze the reason behind the acquisition of these specific results related to creation of non-commutative mutually inverse CET-operations based on model (12). This model is applicable for combining direct and inverse single-operand operations based on modulo 2 addition of corresponding elementary functions. A two-operand CET-operation acquired as a result of such combining will be a tuple of single-operand operations. A non-commutative two-operand CET-operation becomes mutually inverse when tuples of direct and inverse single-operand CET-operations are identical after permutation of operands.

If $C(x)$ is a non-symmetrical single-operand CET-operation, while $C'(x)$ is a CET-operation that is inverse to the former, then a dual-cycle non-commutative mutually inverse CET-operation created on their basis can be presented in the following way:

$$C(x, y) = C(x) \oplus C'(y) = \begin{cases} C_{1*}(x) = C(x) \oplus C'(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ C_{2*}(x) = C(x) \oplus C'(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ C_{3*}(x) = C(x) \oplus C'(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ C_{4*}(x) = C(x) \oplus C'(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \\ C_{5*}(x) = C(x) \oplus C'(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ C_{6*}(x) = C(x) \oplus C'(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ C_{7*}(x) = C(x) \oplus C'(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ C_{8*}(x) = C(x) \oplus C'(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

where * is a sequential number of operation in a tuple of a two-operand operation. This enumeration is independent of the enumeration of single-operand CET-operations from Table 1.

According to model (22), modification of direct single-operand CET-operation is defined by the model of an inverse CET-operation and the value of the second operand. In addition, the model of an inverse CET-operation defines the sequence of the modified direct operations in a tuple of a two-operand CET-operation.

We acquire the following results by permutating operands in CET-operation (22):

$$C(y, x) = C'(x) \oplus C(y) = \begin{cases} C'_{1*}(x) = C'(x) \oplus C(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ C'_{2*}(x) = C'(x) \oplus C(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ C'_{3*}(x) = C'(x) \oplus C(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ C'_{4*}(x) = C'(x) \oplus C(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \\ C'_{5*}(x) = C'(x) \oplus C(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 0 \\ C'_{6*}(x) = C'(x) \oplus C(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 0; y_3 = 1 \\ C'_{7*}(x) = C'(x) \oplus C(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 0 \\ C'_{8*}(x) = C'(x) \oplus C(y), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; y_3 = 1 \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

According to model (23), modification of inverse single-operand CET-operation is defined by the model of direct CET-operation and the value of the second operand. In addition, the model of direct CET-operation defines the sequence of the modified direct operations in a tuple of a two-operand CET-operation.

If two-operand CET-operation (22) is mutually inverse, then CET-operation $C'_{i*}(x)$ is inverse to the direct single-operand CET-operation $C_{i*}(x)$.

According to (22), there exists a total of $8!=40320$ tuples of modified operations. Each tuple is defined only by models of direct and inverse CET-operations. This makes the creation of mutually inverse dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations a very complex task. However, development of a method applicable for synthesis of such operations alongside with evaluation of the complexity of its application goes beyond the scope of this research.

6. Application of dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations

In stream ciphers, the data is generally encrypted based on modulo addition of open data with a pseudorandom sequence. Correspondingly, the data decryption is also based on the modulo addition of encrypted data with the same pseudorandom sequence. It is worth mentioning, that both addressees utilize only the operation of modulo addition for encryption or decryption during data exchange. This is the reason why the utilized encryption and decryption algorithms are identical. An intruder will have to replicate the pseudorandom sequence to hack this kind of stream cipher. Today such stream ciphers are widely used due to the simplicity of their practical application.

It is possible to greatly increase the hacking difficulty by utilizing a symmetrical commutative two-operand CET-operation instead of modulo addition in a stream cipher. Should this scenario occur, then an intruder will have to replicate not only the pseudorandom sequence but the CET-operation as well. We have synthesized a total of 96 two-bit symmetrical commutative two-operand CET-operations as a result of our simulation experiment. An increase of bit value also increases a number of CET-operations that apply to the scenario mentioned above. The downside of utilizing these symmetrical commutative two-operand CET-operations lies in identical encryption and decryption algorithms used by addressees in cryptographic networks.

Dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations alter encryption algorithms when the permutation of operands occurs. Two addresses in a cryptographic system can encrypt data with the identical CET-operation, while one of them permutes the operands, and the other does not. Encrypting the same data with identical pseudorandom sequences results in acquisition of different cryptograms, thus making it significantly more difficult for an intruder to perform a hacking attempt. The downside, however, lies in the necessity to utilize CET-operations for data encryption and inverse CET-operations for data decryption.

This applies for all addressees. The problem can be resolved by using mutually inverse dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations. As a result of permutating the operands in these operations, a direct operation can be modified into an inverse, or vice versa.

Both addresses of cryptographic system will encrypt and decrypt data based on one mutually inverse dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operation if one of them has conducted permutation of operands. In this case, encrypting the same data with identical pseudorandom sequences also results in acquisition of different cryptograms. Application of mutually inverse dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operation does not result in a significant increase in complexity of a cryptographic system compared to application of symmetrical commutative two-operand CET-operations.

We suggest using a group of CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation instead of one two-operand CET-operation to increase cryptographic integrity of stream ciphers based on CET-operations.

We can utilize models for synthesis of groups of operations to an accuracy of permutation of the first/second operand, as well as to an accuracy of permutation of the transformation result to create a group of CET-operations [18].

According to the results of our research, groups of dual-cycle commutative and non-commutative CET-operations are synthesized based on model (1). Practical application of synthesis of groups of CET-operations for direct and inverse cryptographic transformation of data in cryptographic systems has its peculiarities. They are related to the peculiarities of the synthesized groups of operations.

The following model is required to be executed during creation of a symmetrical cryptographic system based on a group of symmetrical commutative two-operand CET-operations based on model (1):

$$C_{\gamma}(x, \gamma_1) = C_{\gamma}(C(x, \gamma_1)) \quad (24)$$

where γ is a pseudorandom key sequence for modification of a CET-operation; γ_1 is a pseudorandom key sequence for execution of a CET-operation.

Because CET-operation $C(x, y)$ is symmetrical, then $C_{\gamma}(x, \gamma_1)$ is symmetrical as well. Thus, the following expression is valid:

$$C_{\gamma}(C_{\gamma}(x, \gamma_1), \gamma_1) = x. \quad (25)$$

According to (24), a cryptographic system is required to have two key sequences. Expression (25) shows that this system will be symmetrical since all modified CET-operations are symmetrical. These operations provide an option for both direct and inverse transformation of data.

We will now analyze the creation of a cryptographic system based on application of a group of dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations.

Addressing the task mentioned above requires an analysis of the creation process of a cryptographic system based on application of a single- or dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operation.

The following expressions are valid for all dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations:

$$\begin{cases} C(x, y) \neq C(y, x) \\ C'(C(x, y), y) = x \\ C'(C(y, x), x) = y \\ C'(x, y) \neq C'(y, x) \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

According to (26), addressee **A** can encrypt data based on model $C(x, \gamma_1)$, while addressee **B** will then decrypt data based on model $C'(x, \gamma_1)$. Correspondingly, addressee **B** can encrypt data based on model $C(\gamma_1, x)$, while addressee **A** will then decrypt data based on model $C'(\gamma_1, x)$. Following this algorithm, addressee **A** will utilize CET-operations $C(x, \gamma_1)$ and $C'(\gamma_1, x)$. Addressee **B** on the other hand will utilize CET-operations $C(\gamma_1, x)$ and $C'(x, \gamma_1)$. According to this cryptographic algorithm, encryption of the same data with identical pseudorandom sequences results in acquisition of different cryptograms.

A dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operation may allow permutation of operands. Thus, according to (26), addressee **A** can encrypt data based on models $C(x, \gamma_1)$ and $C(\gamma_1, x)$, while addressee **B** will correspondingly decrypt data based on models $C'(x, \gamma_1)$ and $C'(\gamma_1, x)$. A proper application of the corresponding cryptographic network requires addressee **A** to store and utilize CET-operations $C(x, \gamma_1)$, $C'(x, \gamma_1)$ and $C'(\gamma_1, x)$. Addressee **B** on the other hand will store and operate with CET-operations $C(x, \gamma_1)$, $C'(x, \gamma_1)$ and $C'(\gamma_1, x)$.

We suggest implementing the third stream encryption scenario [25] to reduce the number of models of CET-operations required to be stored by the addressees for implementation of a cryptographic network based on dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operation. Following this stream encryption scenario, permutation of operands before encryption and decryption provides an option to decrypt a cryptogram by an inverse CET-operation, in which the operands are not permuted. In this case, both addressees **A** and **B** are required to store and utilize only CET-operations $C(x, \gamma_1)$ and $C'(x, \gamma_1)$ to ensure proper implementation of cryptographic network. A pseudorandom control of permutation of operands during encryption of the same data allows the creation of different cryptograms.

A group of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations is created based on model (1). Thus, addressee **A** can encrypt data based on models

$$C_\gamma(x, \gamma_1) = C_\gamma(C(x, \gamma_1)). \quad (27)$$

These models of groups of encryption operations differ from models (24) by applying a non-commutative two-operand CET-operation instead of the commutative one. The expression $C_\gamma(x, \gamma_1) \neq C'_\gamma(x, \gamma_1)$ is valid for this group of CET-operations.

A group of inverse operations to an accuracy of permutation of the first operand is required for data decryption if the data is encrypted by a group of CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of the result [18]. Thus, the decryption of data encrypted based on the group of models (27) will require addressee **B** to use a group of operations for decryption created based on model

$$C'_\gamma(x, \gamma_1) = C'(C'_\gamma(x), \gamma_1). \quad (28)$$

To ensure proper functionality of the cryptographic system created based on models (27) and (28), addressees **A** and **B** must store models used for creation of groups of direct and inverse two-operand CET-operations, as well as groups of direct and inverse single-operand CET-operations. This is done according to the third encryption scenario. Utilization of just the symmetrical single-operand CET-operations drastically reduces the modification options of a non-commutative two-operand CET-operation. Only 10 out of 24 two-bit single-operand CET-operations (13) are symmetrical (Table 3).

We will now analyze the creation of a cryptographic system based on the application of a dual-cycle non-commutative mutually inverse two-operand CET-operation.

The following expressions are valid for all dual-cycle mutually inverse two-operand CET-operations:

$$\begin{cases} C(x, y) \neq C(y, x) \\ C'(x, y) \neq C'(y, x) \\ C'(x, y) = C'(y, x) \\ C'(y, x) = C(x, y) \\ C(y, C(x, y)) = x \\ C(C(y, x), y) = x \end{cases}. \quad (29)$$

According to (29), addressee **A** can encrypt data based on model $C(x, \gamma_1)$, while addressee **B** will then decrypt data based on model $C(\gamma_1, x)$. Correspondingly, addressee **B** can encrypt data based on model $C(\gamma_1, x)$, while addressee **A** will then decrypt data based on model $C(x, \gamma_1)$. Following this algorithm, both addressees **A** and **B** will store and utilize CET-operations $C(x, \gamma_1)$. Addressee **A** encrypts and decrypts data without permutating the operands, while addressee **B**, on the contrary, must permute the operands in $C(x, \gamma_1)$ to conduct encryption or decryption.

In this case, encrypting the same data with identical pseudorandom sequences also results in acquisition of different cryptograms. Because $C(x, y) \neq C(y, x)$, addressees **A** and **B** acquire different cryptograms as a result of permutating the operands while encrypting the same data with the same CET-operation with identical pseudorandom sequences.

An increase in variability and cryptographic integrity of encryption algorithm is possible to achieve by using a group of CET-operations instead of just one operation. The conducted research proves, however, that creating a group of dual-cycle non-commutative mutually inverse two-operand CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation is impossible. It is possible to address this issue by additional encryption of a cryptogram by a symmetrical CET-operation before transmission through the data channel. When such cryptogram is acquired, it must first be decrypted by the same symmetrical CET-operation, which was utilized for its additional encryption. The modified CET-operation itself, which is created by sequential application of mutually inverse CET-operation with symmetrical CET-operation, will not be symmetrical.

We will now analyze options for additional symmetrical encryption.

- Additional symmetrical encryption based on the implementation of a set of symmetrical single-operand CET-operations.

The encryption proceeds based on the following model:

$$C_{\gamma}(x, \gamma_1) = C_{\gamma}(C(x, \gamma_1)) = z \quad (30)$$

where $C(x, \gamma_1)$ is a non-commutative mutually inverse CET-operation; $C_{\gamma}(x, \gamma_1)$ is a modified mutually inverse CET-operation; $C(x)$ is a symmetrical single-operand CET-operation; $C_{\gamma}(x)$ is the specified symmetrical single-operand CET-operation, which is utilized for additional encryption; γ is a pseudorandom key sequence for choosing a symmetrical single-operand CET-operation from the defined set of operations; γ_1 is a pseudorandom key sequence used for execution of a mutually inverse CET-operation; z is the result of encryption.

Model (30) is implemented in two stages. In the first stage, the data is transformed by a non-commutative mutually inverse CET-operation. In the second stage, the encryption result is transformed by the specified symmetrical single-operand CET-operation.

The decryption proceeds based on the following model:

$$C(\gamma_1, C_{\gamma}(z)) = x. \quad (31)$$

The data decryption based on model (31) also proceeds in 2 stages. In the first stage, the acquired cryptogram is transformed by the specified symmetrical single-operand CET-operation. In the second stage, the data is decrypted by a non-commutative mutually inverse CET-operation.

If the encryption is conducted with permutation of operands based on model

$$C_{\gamma}(\gamma_1, x) = C_{\gamma}(C(\gamma_1, x)) = z,$$

then the decryption proceeds based on the following model

$$C(C_{\gamma}(z), \gamma_1) = x.$$

The downside of this option lies in the necessity to store the set of symmetrical single-operand CET-operations. All 10 symmetrical two-bit single-operand CET-operations are presented in set (13). The number of symmetrical three-bit matrix single-operand CET-operations from the base group is 15 operations (Table 6).

- Additional symmetrical encryption based on dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operations.

The encryption proceeds based on the following model:

$$C_{\gamma}(x, \gamma_1) = C_*(C(x, \gamma_1), \gamma) = z \quad (32)$$

where $C(x, \gamma_1)$ is a non-commutative mutually inverse CET-operation; $C_{\gamma}(x, \gamma_1)$ is a modified non-commutative mutually inverse CET-operation; $C_*(x, \gamma)$ is a dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operation, which is utilized for additional encryption; γ is a pseudorandom key sequence for executing a commutative two-operand CET-operation; γ_1 is a pseudorandom key sequence for executing of a mutually inverse CET-operation; z is the result of encryption.

The data encryption based on model (32) proceeds in 2 stages. In the first stage, the data is transformed by a non-commutative mutually inverse CET-operation. In the second stage, the encryption result is transformed by the commutative two-operand CET-operation.

The decryption proceeds based on the following model:

$$C(\gamma_1, C_*(z, \gamma)) = x. \quad (33)$$

The data decryption based on model (33) also proceeds in 2 stages. In the first stage, the acquired cryptogram is transformed by the commutative two-operand CET-operation. In the second stage, the data is decrypted by a non-commutative mutually inverse CET-operation.

If the encryption is conducted with permutation of operands based on model

$$C_{\gamma}(\gamma_1, x) = C_*(C(\gamma_1, x), \gamma) = z, \quad (34)$$

then the decryption proceeds based on the following model

$$C(C_*(z, \gamma), \gamma_1) = x. \quad (35)$$

Permutation of operands in dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operations does not alter the result of the operation's implementation. Thus, models (32) - (35) provide options to use different variations related to permutation of operands in commutative CET-operations, whereas no alteration of the results of data encryption or decryption occurs.

Additional symmetrical encryption based on commutative two-operand CET-operation does not require preservation of the set of symmetrical single-operand CET-operations because the commutative two-operand CET-operation is a formalized set of single-operand CET-operations.

For example, a commutative two-bit two-operand CET-operation consists of 4 single-operand CET-operations, a commutative three-bit two-operand CET-operation consists of 8 single-operand CET-operations, and a commutative four-bit two-operand CET-operation consists of 16 single-operand CET-operations,

- Additional symmetrical encryption based on a group of dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operations.

A group of dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operations is created to an accuracy of permutation of transformation results. This group of CET-operations is executed based on model (1). It is therefore required to combine encryption model based on dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operations (32) with a model for creating a group of dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operations. This allows us to conclude, that the encryption proceeds based on the following model:

$$C_{\gamma}(x, \gamma_1) = C_i(C_*(C(x, \gamma_1), \gamma)) = z \quad (36)$$

where $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$; m is a number of single-operand CET-operations in a group.

All operations from the group of dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operations are symmetrical. Thus, data decryption proceeds based on the following model:

$$C(\gamma_1, C_i(C_*(z, \gamma))) = x. \quad (37)$$

If the encryption is conducted with permutation of operands based on model

$$C_{\gamma}(\gamma_1, x) = C_i(C_*(C(\gamma_1, x), \gamma)) = z, \quad (38)$$

then the decryption proceeds based on the following model

$$C(C_i(C_*(z, \gamma)), \gamma_1) = x. \quad (39)$$

Models (36) - (39) allow permutation of operands in CET-operations from the group of dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operations. The results of data encryption and decryption remain unaffected by these permutations.

Additional symmetrical encryption based on a group of dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operations does requires preservation of the set of symmetrical single-operand CET-operations. For example, if two-bit two-operand CET-operations are chosen for the encryption, then it is required to preserve 24 single-operand CET-operations. These operations allow to conduct the additional symmetrical encryption based on application of one of 4 groups of dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operations. Each group includes 24 dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operations [20]. Thus, the additional symmetrical encryption proceeds with utilization of 24 out of 96 possible substitution tables.

- Additional encryption with utilization of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations.

Permutation of operands does not affect the general result of cryptogram creation and the decryption result in the analyzed scenarios of using the additional symmetrical encryption. Thus, we suggest utilizing symmetrical two-operand CET-operations to increase the number of possible scenarios for setting up cryptographic networks.

CET-operation $C(x, y) = C(C_1(x), C_2(x), \dots, C_n(x))$ is symmetrical ($C(x, y) = C'(x, y)$), if $C_1(x) = C'_1(x)$, $C_2(x) = C'_2(x)$, ..., $C_n(x) = C'_n(x)$, where n is a number of single-operand CET-operations in a tuple of a two-operand operation. A symmetrical two-operand CET-operation is created from a tuple of symmetrical single-operand CET-operations [18]. This allows us to conclude, that a set of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations includes a subset of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations, which do not allow permutation of operands, as well as a subset of commutative two-operand CET-operations. It is important to note, that the number of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations, which do not allow permutation of operands, is much higher than the number of dual-cycle commutative two-operand CET-operations.

The encryption proceeds based on the following model:

$$C_\gamma(x, \gamma_1) = C(C(x, \gamma_1), \gamma) = z \quad (40)$$

where $C(x, \gamma_1)$ is a non-commutative mutually inverse CET-operation; $C_\gamma(x, \gamma_1)$ is a modified mutually inverse CET-operation; $C(x, \gamma)$ is a symmetrical two-operand CET-operation, which is utilized for additional encryption; γ is a pseudorandom key sequence for executing a symmetrical two-operand CET-operation; γ_1 is a pseudorandom key sequence for executing of a mutually inverse CET-operation; z is the result of encryption.

The decryption proceeds based on the following model:

$$C(\gamma_1, C(z, \gamma)) = x. \quad (41)$$

If the encryption is conducted with permutation of operands based on model

$$C_\gamma(\gamma_1, x) = C(C(\gamma_1, x), \gamma) = z, \quad (42)$$

then the decryption proceeds based on the following model

$$C(C(z, \gamma), \gamma_1) = x. \quad (43)$$

The following expressions are valid for most symmetrical two-operand CET-operations:

$$\begin{cases} C(C(x, \gamma), \gamma) = x \\ C(\gamma, C(\gamma, x)) \neq x \end{cases}$$

Therefore, models (40) - (43) do not allow permutation of operands in symmetrical two-operand CET-operations because these permutations prevent the decryption of data.

The number of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations usable in models (40) - (43) is defined as a number of combinations with n by m [18],

$$C_n^m = \frac{n!}{m!(n-m)!}$$

where n is a number of symmetrical single-operand CET-operations; m is a number of symmetrical single-operand CET-operations in a tuple of a symmetrical two-operand CET-operation.

If symmetrical two-bit two-operand CET-operations are utilized for additional encryption, then according to Table 3 and (13) their number is defined as follows:

$$C_{10}^4 = \frac{10!}{4!(10-4)!} = 30.$$

Every operation out of the total of 30 symmetrical two-bit two-operand CET-operations operates with 4 substitution tables, which are chosen at random depending on \mathcal{V} .

If three-bit two-operand matrix CET-operations from the base group are utilized for additional encryption, then according to Table 6:

$$C_{13}^8 = \frac{13!}{8!(13-8)!} = 1287.$$

Every operation out of the total of 1287 symmetrical three-bit two-operand CET-operations operates with 8 substitution tables, which are chosen at random depending on \mathcal{V} .

- Additional encryption with utilization of a group of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations.

A group of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations is created to an accuracy of permutation of the second operand [18]. This allows us to conclude, that the encryption proceeds based on the following model:

$$C_{\gamma^*}(x, \gamma_1) = C(C(x, \gamma_1), C_*(\gamma)) = z \quad (44)$$

where $C(x, \gamma_1)$ is a non-commutative mutually inverse CET-operation; $C_{\gamma^*}(x, \gamma_1)$ is a modified mutually inverse CET-operation; $C(x, \gamma)$ is a symmetrical two-operand CET-operation, which is utilized for additional encryption; $C_*(\gamma)$ is a single-operand CET-operation for modification of the second operand; $C_*(\gamma)$ is a pseudorandom key sequence for executing a symmetrical two-operand CET-operation; γ_1 is a pseudorandom key sequence for executing of a mutually inverse CET-operation; z is the result of encryption.

The decryption proceeds based on the following model:

$$C(\gamma_1, C(z, C_*^l(\gamma))) = x. \quad (45)$$

where $C_*^l(\gamma)$ is an inverse single-operand CET-operation for modification of the second operand.

If the encryption is conducted with permutation of operands based on model

$$C_{\gamma^*}(\gamma_1, x) = C(C(\gamma_1, x), C_*(\gamma)) = z, \quad (46)$$

then the decryption proceeds based on the following model

$$C(C(z, C'_*(\gamma)), \gamma_1) = x. \quad (47)$$

Usage of a group of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations in models (44) - (47) can, in theory, increase the number of modifications of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations, which are used in cryptographic algorithms. A total of 24 modifications can be made for every operation out of 30 symmetrical two-bit two-operand CET-operations according to Table 3. In addition, a total of 28 modifications can be synthesized for every operation out of 1287 symmetrical three-bit two-operand matrix CET-operations from the base group. These modifications are synthesized based on single-operand matrix CET-operations from the base group (Table 6). It is worth mentioning that utilization of a group of CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of the second operand does not increase the number of single-operand CET-operations, which are used during encryption. On the other hand, utilization of a group of the modified CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of the second operand increases the sequence period of the pseudorandom sequence of single-operand CET-operations, which serve as the foundation for the cryptographic transformation of data.

Overall, developers of cryptographic algorithms can apply the proposed models to achieve the design goals while operating under conditions of limited resources within a cryptographic system.

7. Conclusions

1. We have divided the non-commutative two-operand CET-operations into dual- and triple-cycle non-commutative CET-operations. We have also analyzed the attributes of each group. Finally, we have defined a group of mutually inverse CET-operations among the dual-cycle non-commutative two-operand CET-operations. Permutation of operands in these mutually inverse operations provides an option to move from the direct cryptographic transformation to the inverse.

2. We have developed methods applicable for synthesis of the dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations according to the results of our research. The method for synthesis of groups of dual-cycle non-commutative CET-operations allows generation of pseudorandom sequences of data modifications of CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of the results. We have also analyzed the options for creating cryptographic systems based on dual-cycle commutative and non-commutative CET-operations. Another object of our analysis was the peculiarities of creating cryptographic systems with a generation of pseudorandom sequences of CET-operations. Finally, we have analyzed the variability of these systems.

3. We have analyzed the limitations for creation and usage of the dual-cycle mutually inverse CET-operations. We have established that the generation of a pseudorandom sequence of mutually inverse CET-operations is impossible. We have also researched the possibility of increasing the variability of cryptographic algorithms based on the dual-cycle mutually inverse CET-operations by using additional symmetrical single- or two-operand CET-operations.

4. The acquired results allow us to develop the data encryption algorithms under conditions of limited resources within a cryptographic system. These limitations are very common in both mobile and stationary systems of limited resource cryptographic data security.

5. As a topic for future research, we suggest developing an algorithm for the creation of mutually inverse CET-operations, which applies to computer realization.

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Conflict of interests

We hereby declare that there is no conflict of interest of any kind regarding this research, which could potentially affect it and its outcome. This includes financial conflicts, personal conflicts, conflicts regarding the authorship, etc.

Finances and investments

We've conducted this research without any financial support and investments.

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